

THE OUTPUT ORIENTED TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY OF INDIAN MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN THE POST- REFORM ERA

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Abstract

The study evaluates Output Oriented Technical Efficiency (OTE) of Indian manufacturing firms across industries using Non-parametric DEA on the CMIE Prowess Database from March-1995 to March-2016. Result indicates the rise in OTE from 0.852 to 0.874 over the study-period. Sample firms have the potential of 10.3% increase in output with efficient input utilization. Leather achieved the highest mean OTE of 0.954, while chemicals had the lowest at 0.835. Around 31% of firms demonstrated output efficiency with a score of one. A simultaneous panel regression analysed OTE alongside advertising intensity (ADV), marketing intensity (MKT), R&D intensity (RD), and net exports intensity (NX), revealing these factors significantly impacting firms' OTE. Notably, OTE also influenced these strategic variables significantly across industries. Recommendations for enhancing OTE involve strategic enhancements in advertising, marketing, R&D, and net exports, aimed at improving firms' overall performance.

Keywords: Total factor productivity growth, Manufacturing Sector, Indian Economy

JEL Classifications: D24, L60, O530

1. Introduction

The manufacturing industry is the backbone of economic development of a country. The expansion of this industry is used to measure the economic strength of the country. This industry helps in modernizing the agricultural sector (Elizabethrani, 2019). The manufacturing sector is capable of reducing the heavy dependence of people on agriculture by generating huge employment in secondary sector. There is a growing emphasis put on the service sector globally. But there exists an established inter-sectoral linkage between service and the manufacturing sectors (Park, 1994). Thus, the service sector growth also depends upon the growth of the manufacturing sector. The development of the manufacturing sector in proper channel can strengthen the base of the economy as a whole. The increase in efficiency of manufacturing sector can also absorb different economic shocks (Kendrick (1956), Solow (1957), Denison (1967), Jorgenson and Griliches (1967)).

In early 1990s, the economic reform was initiated in India which acted as a shock to the economy because previously the Indian manufacturing industry was protected from tough foreign competition through various restrictive government regulations. But, after 1991, the government policies gradually became less friendly for inefficient firms (Bhandari & Maiti, 2007). Thus, the efficiency of a manufacturing firm became pre-requisite for growth as well as for the survival of the firms during the post-reform era.

This change in the economic policy has raised some very interesting questions. One issue is related to the extent of

efficiency of the Indian manufacturing firms in the post-reform era. Additional query may be: which determinants are held responsible for significantly influencing the output oriented technical efficiency (OTE) of Indian manufacturing firms during this period.

These issues are very much relevant in the changed economic scenario in India. The major objective of present paper is to examine these stated aspects of Indian manufacturing firms in the post-reform period. For this purpose, the present study has considered the following nine Indian manufacturing industry groups: chemical industry, food products industry, leather industry, machinery industry, metal industry, non-metallic mineral products industry, paper industry, textile industry and transport industry. All the industry groups under Indian manufacturing sector have been initially incorporated but subject to the availability of data, the above mentioned nine industry groups have finally been selected.

It is well-known that there are two alternative concepts of efficiency. One is allocative efficiency and the other one is technical efficiency. The present study focuses on technical efficiency. Technical efficiency can be measured either input-oriented (the ratio of minimum level of input required to produce a given level of output to the actual input used to produce that given level of output) or output-oriented approach (the ratio of actual output produced to the maximum level of output that can be produced given the input usage). The present study will consider only output oriented approach.

In this connection, the existing studies have been briefly reviewed. Driffield and Kambhampati (2003) showed that the overall efficiency in the post-reform period increased in five out of their considered six manufacturing sectors. The analysis of Mazumdar and Rajeev (2009) indicated that increased export earnings did not necessarily lead to higher efficiency of Indian Pharmaceutical firms. Bhandari and Maiti (2012) presented a direct association between the size of the firm and technical efficiency of Indian leather firms. Kumar and Arora (2012) showed a steep fall in the level of technical efficiency in post-reform period as compared to the post reform period. Saravanakumar and Kim (2012) revealed that the reform improved the efficiency of heavy industries but failed to improve efficiency in light industries. Parameswaran (2004) estimated technical change and technical efficiency change using a stochastic frontier production function for Indian capital goods industries during 1990s. This study showed that these industries experienced a significant improvement in the rate of technological progress but decline in level of technical efficiency during the post reform period. Mazumdar, Rajeev and Ray (2012) used non-parametric approach of DEA to examine the sources of heterogeneity in the efficiency of Indian pharmaceutical firms for the period 1991-2005. They found that these firms could make efficient use of their inputs but output efficiency was declining during this period. Bhandari and Ray (2011) used data from Annual Survey of Industries (ASI) for a number of years 1985-86, 1990-91, 1996-97, 1998-99, 1999-00, 2001-02 to measure the technical

efficiency in the Indian textile industry at firm level. Their analysis suggested that the size of the firm would have a direct effect on technical efficiency, implying the small firms must get consolidated to build large entities which might enhance efficiency.

There exists a nexus relationship between the Indian manufacturing firms' performances and different strategic variables in the post-reform era (Chen & Ibhagui (2019), Pyper et al. (2022), Gakii & Maina (2019) etc.). Different strategic variables may be endogenous in nature. For example, Advertising Intensity (ADV), Marketing Intensity (MKT), R&D Intensity (RD) and Net Export Intensity (NX) may not only affect the firms' performance indicators like OTE but in turn they may get affected by this performance indicator. Thus, there may be inter-connection between these variables. There is dearth in the studies highlighting these simultaneous relationships. The present study fills up this gap and contributes to the literature in this direction. The study finds out the determinants of OTE in a simultaneous panel set up. For determinant analysis, a simultaneous panel model as developed by Baltagi (EC2SLS random-effects Instrumental Variable regression) has been performed for OTE Block considering the endogenous variables OTE, ADV, MKT, RD and NX. This type study is very important for framing appropriate policies to boost up the performance level of Indian manufacturing firms.

The paper unfolds as follows: Section 2 reports data sources. Section 3 presents the estimated results of output oriented technical efficiency of firms. Section 4 represents the determinant analysis and Section 5 concludes the study.

2. Data Sources

Data regarding the Input-Output variables for estimating OTE has been collected from CMIE Prowess Database

for the time period March, 1995 – March, 2016. Total number of manufacturing firms incorporated is 820.

Table 1. Composition of Manufacturing Firms (Sample details)

Manufacturing firms	No. of Firms	Percentage (%)
Chemicals & chemical products (Chemical Industry)	223	27.20
Food Products, beverages & tobacco (Food Product Industry)	34	4.15
Leather & related products (Leather Industry)	11	1.34
Machinery industry	150	18.29
Metal & metal products (Metal Industry)	114	13.90
Non- metallic mineral products	46	5.62
Paper & paper products (Paper Industry)	25	3.05
Textile industry	125	15.24
Transport & Transport equipment (Transport Industry)	92	11.22
Total	820	100

The study conceptualizes a 1-output and 5-inputs production technology. The output is the total sales of the firm deflated by the WPI for manufacturing products (base 1993-94 =100). The inputs are: (i) Raw Material inputs (measured in terms of the companies' expenditure on raw materials, stores and spares) deflated by the WPI for manufacturing products (base 1993-94 =100) , (ii) Energy and water Input (measured in terms of the expenditure of the companies for power, fuel and water) deflated by WPI of power & fuel (base 1993-94 =100) , (iii) Labour (measured in terms of wages and

salaries of the workers) and nominal wage has been deflated by WPI (base 1993-94 = 100), (iv) Land (measured in terms of rent & lease rent paid) deflated by WPI (base 1993-94 = 100), and (v) Capital (measured in terms of value of the net fixed assets) deflated by WPI of machinery (base: 1993-94 =100).

3. Results

Estimated results of Output Oriented Technical Efficiency of Manufacturing Firms

The output-oriented efficiency score of the companies is obtained on the basis of a computer program DEAP Version 2.1, developed by Tim Coelli.

Table 2. Mean Output Oriented Technical Efficiency over Years

Year	Chem	Fd Prod	Leat	Mach	Met	Non met	Paper	Tex	Trans	Mean
1995	0.76	0.83	0.89	0.92	0.71	0.95	0.93	0.75	0.94	0.85
1996	0.80	0.88	0.91	0.91	0.90	0.94	0.95	0.89	0.94	0.90
1997	0.76	0.90	0.96	0.92	0.94	0.95	0.89	0.87	0.94	0.90
1998	0.74	0.87	0.97	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.90	0.90	0.95	0.90
1999	0.84	0.89	0.93	0.91	0.95	0.96	0.88	0.91	0.92	0.91

2000	0.92	0.89	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.87	0.92	0.94	0.92
2001	0.92	0.89	0.97	0.90	0.93	0.97	0.86	0.77	0.93	0.90
2002	0.87	0.84	0.95	0.91	0.93	0.97	0.89	0.84	0.91	0.90
2003	0.87	0.84	0.93	0.85	0.89	0.95	0.88	0.88	0.91	0.89
2004	0.81	0.87	1.00	0.90	0.91	0.84	0.88	0.90	0.93	0.89
2005	0.81	0.87	0.99	0.94	0.93	0.83	0.93	0.88	0.94	0.90
2006	0.84	0.88	0.93	0.94	0.95	0.72	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.89
2007	0.88	0.87	0.98	0.94	0.91	0.75	0.90	0.88	0.93	0.89
2008	0.87	0.87	0.97	0.94	0.81	0.84	0.92	0.88	0.96	0.90
2009	0.88	0.88	0.93	0.86	0.83	0.91	0.92	0.87	0.96	0.89
2010	0.86	0.88	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.86	0.95	0.91
2011	0.82	0.86	0.97	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.89	0.86	0.95	0.90
2012	0.89	0.85	0.98	0.91	0.90	0.84	0.90	0.86	0.95	0.90
2013	0.92	0.89	0.98	0.93	0.89	0.93	0.92	0.87	0.95	0.92
2014	0.87	0.89	0.97	0.85	0.91	0.92	0.90	0.89	0.89	0.90
2015	0.73	0.89	0.97	0.92	0.89	0.90	0.89	0.84	0.92	0.88
2016	0.72	0.83	0.96	0.89	0.93	0.90	0.91	0.78	0.95	0.87

Source: Compiled by the Author

Table 2 shows that the mean OTE was highest (i.e. 0.924) in 2000 and lowest (i.e. 0.852) in 1995 for the present sample. The mean OTE score was not one for any of the years. The mean OTE

has been increased from 0.852 in 1995 to 0.874 in 2016. The year-wise mean OTE of each industry has been reported in this table.

Table 3. Mean OTE (all the years taken together) for Different Industry-Groups

Industry	Mean OTE
Chemical	0.835
Food Products	0.871
Leather	0.954
Machinery	0.911
Metal	0.900
Non-metallic mineral products	0.899
Paper	0.903
Textile	0.864
Transport	0.936
Grand Mean	0.897

Source: Compiled by the Author

Table 3 shows that The Grand OTE is 0.897 for the current sample. This indicates that the scarce resources have been inefficiently used during the study period. If the inputs are efficiently used, then the additional

10.3% output can be produced by utilizing the same level of inputs. It also shows that the mean OTE is the highest (0.954) for leather industry and the lowest (0.835) for chemical industry.

Table 4. Percentage of Efficient Firms for all Industry-Groups (OTE)

Industry	% of Efficient Firms
Chemical	14
Food Products	28
Leather	64
Machinery	18
Metal	23
Non-metallic mineral products	32
Paper	55
Textile	18
Transport	23
Grand Mean	31

Source: Compiled by the Author

Table 4 shows that about 31% of sample manufacturing firms are output efficient on an average. They are having the efficiency score of one. It shows that the highest 64% of sample firms of leather industries are output-efficient whereas the lowest 14% of sample firms in chemical industry are output-efficient.

4. Determinants of Output Oriented Technical Efficiency (OTE)

A second stage panel regression has been carried out to relate the OTE of the Indian manufacturing firms with the strategic variables perused by firms as well as firms' characteristics namely R&D Intensity, Net Export Intensity, Advertising Intensity, Marketing Intensity, Age, Diversification Index and Size of the company. The explanations for the inclusion of different explanatory variables can be summarized as follows:

(i) Advertising Intensity (ADV):

This variable is measured by advertising expenditure as a ratio to total sales. Advertising is used as the instrument to lower the scope and

effectiveness of price competition by creating product differentiation among different firms in the consumer goods industries. Goldar et al. (2004) and Carod and Blasco (2004) pointed out the relationship between advertising intensity and technical efficiency for the Indian Engineering goods industries and Spanish manufacturing firms respectively.

(ii) Marketing Intensity (MKT):

This variable is measured by marketing expenditure as a ratio to total sales. It can be as a proxy for product differentiation. Kao et al. (2006) evaluates technical efficiency and allocative efficiency in marketing and gets a direct relationship between return and marketing expenditure. The return can be in the form of increased sales or increased.

(iii) R&D Intensity (RD):

This variable is measured by R&D expenditure as a ratio to total sales. Some studies are available which are showing the linkage between the R&D activities and efficiency of the firm for Indian industry, for instance,

Ferrantino, (1995), Driffield and Kambhampti (2003), MAZUMDER ET AL. (2010).

(iv) Net Export Intensity (NX):

There is a common opinion that export improves the efficiency of the firms (Balassa, 1988). The economic policies under export-led growth strategy support the argument that the exposure to the international market through the channel of export helps to increase the efficiency of exporters. Similarly, advocates of endogenous growth theory believe that export is playing a significant role by increasing efficiency through innovation (Grossman and Helpman, 1991) and technology transfer (Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1995). The empirical evidence showing that firms which will become exporters have some prior benefits is very rich and unambiguous. Mention may be made of studies by **Chen and Tang** (1987), Sun et al. (1999), Walujadi (2004), Mok et al. (2010).

World Bank Report (1993, 1997) discussed about the import of foreign technology by the firm and its positive effect on its efficiency. The abolition of the quantitative restrictions on imports and reduction of the customs duties in the post liberalization era in India must have improved the access to imported raw materials and capital goods to enter into the domestic economy. The imports of raw materials embodying latest technologies should increase the efficiency of the firms. In the context of India, a direct relationship between technical efficiency and imports has been reported by Goldar et al. (2004) and Mazumder et al. (2010).

The above discussion reveals that the exports and imports both will improve efficiency. Thus, it may be interesting to find out the relative strength of exports

vis á vis imports in enhancing efficiency. In order to find out this relative role the present paper takes net export intensity (**NX**) i.e. net export as a ratio to total sales as an explanatory variable while determining efficiency.

(v) Diversification Index (DIVIND):

DIVIND of a particular industry group captures the effect of market structure on efficiency of the firms. DIVIND is the reciprocal of concentration ratio. The Herfindahl Index or Concentration Index is calculated as follows: $H = \sum s_i^2$; where s_i is the market share of the i^{th} firm in the market and N is the number of firms.

A negative relation between CR and efficiency is expected by some researchers because competition may lead to cost-consciousness and drive for technological advancement. Others point out the benefits of large size, secured market and expect a direct association between CR and efficiency. The conclusion from the empirical literature also varies and does not provide us a uniform answer [(Katz, 1969), (Kendrick, 1973)].

(vi) AGE:

There are counter arguments regarding the effect of age on firm's performances. One argument is that older firms are displaying superior performances since they are more experienced (Stinchcombe, 1965). On the other hand, the counter argument is that older firms do lack enough flexibility to adopt quickly to the changing economic circumstances which the younger firms can do much more rapidly and efficiently (Marshall, 1920).

The present study has divided the sample companies into two groups:

Agedum } 1 (if Mean Age of the firm < Grand Mean Age)
 } 0 (Otherwise)

0 (Otherwise)

Size:

The efficiency differs due to difference in relative size. A larger sized firm may have an easier access to cheaper and superior quality inputs. It is easier for such firms to exploit economies of scale. They can widen scope of production by making its operation more effective which allows them to perform better compared to smaller firms (Penrose,1959). The present study divides the sample basis on investment into three groups, on the basis of Investment in plant & machinery or equipment according to MSME Classification:

<i>Small dum</i>	1 if mean investment < 5 Cr. rupees
	0 (Otherwise)

<i>Medium dum</i>	1 if mean investment < 10 Cr. rupees
	0 (Otherwise)

<i>Largedum</i>	1 if mean investment > 10 Cr. rupees
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In order to avoid dummy variable trap, Mediumdum has been dropped.

It may be possible that the effect of different explanatory variables may be non-linear in nature. To get this effect, the sole effect of different variables, their square terms and the joint effect of different variables will be incorporated. The effects of the lag value (one year lag) of different strategic variables (i.e. the effects of different strategic variable in the previous period) have also been considered.

4.1 Explaining the Factors Significantly influencing OTE of the Firms: The Results from a Two Stage Least Square Type Approach in a Simultaneous Panel Model

The determinant analysis is based on the estimation of a simultaneous panel model consisting of the equations specifying the determination of OTE, ADV, MKT, RD, NX. Since the present study is mainly interested in finding out the determinants of OTE, to keep my article within limit, I am only reporting the summary result regarding the effects of different variables on OTE and the effect of OTE on different strategic variables.

Table 5. Effect of Different Firm’s Characteristics on OTE

Effect of Different Firm’s Characteristics on OTE	Significant Effect on OTE		Industry
	Direct Effect		
Agedum	Direct Effect	Positive	chemical and textile industries
		Negative	metal industry
	Indirect Effect	Positive	-----
		Negative	through ADV, RD and NX in the leather industry
DIVIND		Positive	leather, paper and textile industries

	Direct Effect	Negative	chemical, machinery, non-metallic mineral products and transport industries
	Indirect Effect	Positive	through ADV and NX in metal industry
		Negative	through ADV, MKT and RD in the food products industry
Largedum	Direct Effect	Positive	-----
		Negative	textile industry
	Indirect Effect	Positive	through RD in chemical industry and through ADV in machinery industry
		Negative	through ADV in leather industry
Smalldum	Direct Effect	Positive	-----
		Negative	-----
	Indirect Effect	Positive	through RD in leather industry and through ADV in paper industry
		Negative	through ADV and MKT in food products industry
REER	Negative Indirect Effect		through NX in food products, machinery, non-metallic mineral products industries

Source: Calculated by the Author

Table 5 shows the effect of different firm's characteristics on OTE of Indian manufacturing firms. Agedum has direct positive effect on OTE in chemical and textile industries, indicating that the younger firms are more output-efficient than the older firms. Agedum has negative direct effect on OTE in metal industry, where the older firms are more output-efficient than the younger firms. In leather industry, agedum has negative indirect effect on OTE through ADV, RD and NX implying that the older firms are doing higher ADV, RD and NX than the younger firms as these are the significant determinants of OTE, OTE will be affected.

DIVIND has direct positive effect on OTE in leather, paper, and textile industries. As the market share gets diversified, OTE of firms increases in these industries. DIVIND has positive indirect effect on OTE through ADV and NX in metal industry. As the

market share gets diversified in this industry, ADV and NX of the firms increases, as a result their output-efficiency of the firms will be affected. DIVIND has negative direct effect on OTE in chemical, machinery, non-metallic mineral products, and transport industries, in which OTE of the firms increases as the market gets concentrated in the hands of few large firms. DIVIND has negative indirect effect on OTE through ADV, MKT and RD in the food products industry. In this industry, as the market gets concentrated, ADV, MKT and RD of the sample firms, which are significant determinants of OTE, increase; as a result, their output-efficiency increases. Largedum has positive indirect effect on OTE through RD in chemical industry and through ADV in machinery industry, meaning that the larger sized firms are having higher levels RD in chemical industry and ADV in machinery industry than the

smaller sized firms. RD in chemical industry and ADV in machinery industry are the significant determinants of OTE; so, their output-efficiency increases. Largedum has negative direct effect on OTE in textile industry, implying that the smaller sized firms are more output efficient than the larger sized firms in this industry. Largedum has negative indirect effect on OTE through ADV in leather industry. In this industry, smaller sized firms are having higher level of ADV which is significant determinant of OTE; as a result, their output-efficiency increases. Smalldum has positive indirect effect on OTE through RD in leather industry and through ADV in paper industry. The smaller firms are having higher levels of RD in leather industry and ADV in paper industry than the larger firms. RD in leather industry and ADV in

paper industry are the significant determinants of OTE; as a result, they have become more output-efficient than the larger firms. Smalldum has negative indirect effect on OTE through ADV and MKT in food products industry. The larger firms are higher levels of ADV and MKT (which are significant determinants of OTE) than the smaller firms in this industry. As a result, they have become more output-efficient.

REER has indirect negative effect on OTE through NX in food products, machinery, non-metallic mineral products industries. An increase in nation's REER is an indication that its exports are becoming costlier and its imports are becoming cheaper. It is losing its trade competitiveness; as a result, NX falls. When REER falls, NX of the firms increases; as a result, their OTE increases.

Table 6. Direct Effect of Strategic Variables on OTE

Direct Effect of Strategic Variables on OTE	Positive Significant Effect has been reached	Positive Effect has not been reached yet
	(Value of the Explanatory Variable) > (Critical level of the Explanatory Variable)	(Value of the Explanatory Variable) < (Critical level of the Explanatory Variable)
ADV	chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile and transport industries	leather industry
MKT	chemical, food products, leather, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper and transport industries	machinery and textile industries
RD	chemical, food products, leather, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, and textile industries	transport industry
NX	chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile and transport industries (exports dominate over imports)	leather and paper industries (imports dominate over exports)

Source: Calculated by the Author

The determinant analysis of OTE as presented in Table 6 suggests that current-period ADV has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile and transport industries, implying that increase in ADV increases OTE. But ADV has U-relationship with OTE with negative marginal effect in leather industry. Increase in ADV being the sunk cost will not initially result in the rise in OTE but its positive effect on OTE can be felt by the leather industry when the mean level of ADV of this industry will exceed the critical level of ADV beyond which its positive effect on OTE can be achieved. As the mean level of ADV is lesser than the critical level of ADV, the positive marginal effect of ADV on OTE has not been obtained yet. Further increase in ADV is recommended to get its positive marginal effect on OTE by the leather industry.

Current-period MKT has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, leather, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, and transport industries, meaning that rise in MKT increases OTE. MKT has U-relationship with OTE with negative marginal effect in machinery and textile industries. Initially the increase in MKT increases the cost of production in these industries, as a result OTE falls. But when the critical level of MKT is reached, its positive effect on OTE will be experienced by these industries. As

they are not doing adequate MKT, their mean MKT is still lesser than the critical level of MKT; for that they have not received the positive effect of MKT on OTE yet. Further increase in MKT is suggested to get its positive marginal effect on OTE by these industries.

The marginal effect of current-period RD on OTE is positive in chemical, food products, leather, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper and textile industries, implying that increase in RD increases OTE. RD has U-relationship with OTE with negative marginal effect in transport industry. The transport industry is not doing sufficient RD to experience the positive of RD on OTE. Further increase in RD is needed to get its positive marginal effect on OTE.

Current-period NX has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile, and transport industries, in which the effect of exports dominates over the effect of imports; resulting in its positive marginal effect of on OTE. Current-period NX has negative marginal effect on OTE in leather and paper industries. The industries are experiencing greater relative strength of imports over exports, as a result they are facing negative marginal effect of NX on OTE. These industries are dependent more on the imported inputs for increasing their output-efficiency.

Table 7. Effect of Lagged Value of Different Strategic Variables on OTE

Effect of Lagged Value (One Year Lag) of Different Strategic Variables on OTE	Positive effect on OTE has been achieved
ADV of the previous period	non-metallic mineral product and transport industries
MKT of the previous period	machinery industry

RD of the previous period	chemical and transport industries
NX of the previous period	chemical, leather, and paper industries

Source: Calculated by the Author

Table 7 represents that previous-period ADV has positive effect on OTE in non-metallic mineral product and transport industries. Here increase in previous-period ADV increases current-period OTE. Previous-period MKT has positive effect on OTE in machinery industry, in which the increase in previous-period MKT will lead to the rise in current-period OTE. Previous-

period RD has positive effect on OTE in chemical and transport industries. Here the rise in previous-period RD increases the current-period OTE. Previous-period NX has positive effect on OTE in chemical, leather, and paper industries, implying that increase in previous-period NX increases current-period OTE.

Table 8. Effect of Different Joint Interaction terms on OTE

Effect of Different Joint Interaction terms on OTE	Positive effect has been achieved
(RD of the current period and NX of the previous period)	chemical and leather industries
(ADV & MKT)	food products industry
(NX & RD)	food products, paper and textile industries
(RD & ADV)	machinery and paper industries

Source: Calculated by the Author

Table 8 suggests that there exists a joint interaction term of RD of the current period and NX of the previous period which has positive effect on OTE in the chemical and leather industries. By participating in the international trade in the previous period, these industries adopt foreign technologies; as a result, RD of the current period increases which in turn increases OTE. Thus, the effect of RD on OTE in the current period in these industries depends highly upon NX in the previous period. There is another joint interaction term of ADV and MKT which is having positive effect on OTE in food products industry. OTE of food products industry being the consumer good producing industry increases with the simultaneous rise in ADV and MKT in the current period. The effect of ADV on OTE depends on MKT and vice-versa.

There is also the existence of another joint interaction term of NX and RD which has positive effect on OTE in food products, paper and textile industries. Through RD, the product quality gets enhanced; as a result, there will be an increase in NX which will lead to the rise in OTE in these industries in the current period. In these industries, the effect of RD on OTE depends on NX and vice-versa.

The machinery and paper industries also get a positive composite effect of RD and ADV on OTE. Through RD, new advertising strategies will be invented; as a result, OTE rises. In these industries, the effect of RD on OTE depends on ADV and vice-versa.

The paper industry also gets another positive composite effect of RD and MKT on OTE. Through RD, new marketing strategies will be invented; as a result, OTE rises. In this industry,

the effect of RD on OTE depends on MKT and vice-versa.

Table 9. Effects of OTE on Different Strategic Variables

Industry	Effect of OTE	Positive Significant effect of OTE has been achieved on the following Strategic Variables	Positive Effect of OTE has not been reached yet on the following Strategic Variables (Value of OTE) < (Critical Level of OTE beyond which its positive effect is achieved)
Chemical		ADV, MKT, NX	RD
Food Products		ADV, MKT, RD, NX	-----
Leather		ADV, MKT, RD, NX	-----
Machinery		MKT, NX	ADV, RD
Metal		MKT, RD, NX	ADV
Non-metallic mineral product		ADV, MKT, RD, NX	-----
Paper		ADV, MKT	RD, NX
Textile		ADV, MKT, RD, NX	-----
Transport		ADV, RD, NX	MKT

Source: Calculated by the Author

Table 9 is representing the effects of OTE on different strategic variables in different manufacturing industries in India. OTE has positive marginal effect on ADV, MKT, RD and NX in the current period in food products, leather, non-metallic mineral products, and textile industries and on ADV, MKT and NX in chemical industry, on MKT and NX in machinery industry, on MKT, RD and NX in metal industry, on ADV and MKT in paper industry, on ADV, RD and NX in transport industry. Increase in OTE increases these strategic variables in the current period in these industries which will further boost up OTE.

In chemical industry, OTE has U-relationship with RD with negative marginal effect as the mean level of OTE is lesser than the critical level of OTE beyond which its positive effect can be felt. The positive effect of OTE on RD will be achieved by the chemical industry when the mean level of OTE will exceed the critical level of OTE. As

mean level of OTE is lesser than the critical level of OTE, its positive marginal effect on RD has not been felt yet. Further increase in OTE is recommended.

In machinery industry, OTE has U-relationship with ADV and RD with negative marginal effect. The positive effect of OTE on ADV and RD will be achieved by this industry when the mean OTE will cross the critical level of OTE. Further increase in OTE is needed.

In metal industry, OTE has U-relationship with ADV with negative marginal effect. The positive marginal effect of OTE on ADV will be experienced by the metal industry when the mean OTE will exceed the critical OTE. Thus, further increase in OTE is suggested.

In paper industry, OTE has U-relationship with RD and NX with negative marginal effect. The positive effect of OTE on RD and NX will be achieved by it when its mean OTE will

be greater than the critical level of OTE for receiving its positive marginal effect.

In transport industry, OTE has U-relationship with MKT with negative marginal effect as the mean OTE is lesser than the critical level of OTE beyond which its positive effect can be got. Further increase in OTE is required so that the critical level of OTE is reached to derive its positive marginal effect.

5. Conclusion & Policy Suggestions

The estimated results of OTE of the present sample suggest that mean OTE is 0.897. The extra 10.3% output can be produced by utilizing the same level of inputs if the efficient utilisation of inputs is done. The mean OTE is the highest (0.954) for leather industry and the lowest (0.835) for chemical industry. About 31% of sample firms are output-efficient implying that these firms are having the efficiency score of one. The mean OTE was highest (i.e., 0.924) in 2000 and lowest (i.e., 0.852) in 1995. The mean OTE has been increased from 0.852 to 0.874 over the study period.

The determinant analysis of OTE suggests that the current-period ADV has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile, and transport industries. But ADV has U-relationship with negative marginal effect in leather industry as mean ADV is lesser than critical level of ADV after which the positive effect is obtained. Thus, further increase in ADV is recommended.

Current-period MKT has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, leather, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper and transport industries. MKT has U-

relationship with negative marginal effect in machinery and textile industries as mean MKT is smaller than critical MKT beyond which the positive effect is felt, so further increase in MKT is suggested.

The marginal effect of current-period RD on OTE is positive in chemical, food products, leather, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper and textile industries. RD has U-relationship with negative marginal effect in transport industry. This industry is recommended to do adequate RD so the mean RD exceeds critical RD to get its positive effect.

Current-period NX has positive marginal effect on OTE in chemical, food products, machinery, metal, non-metallic mineral products, paper, textile, and transport industries, implying the dominant effect of exports over import. Current-period NX has negative marginal effect on OTE in leather and paper industries, implying that these industries are experiencing greater dominance of imports over exports.

In the current period, OTE has positive marginal effect on ADV, MKT, RD and NX in food products, leather, non-metallic mineral products, and textile industries, on ADV, MKT and NX in chemical industry, on MKT and NX in machinery industry, on MKT, RD and NX in metal industry, on ADV and MKT in paper industry, on ADV, RD and NX in transport industry.

OTE has U-relationship with negative marginal effect with RD in chemical industry, with ADV and RD in machinery industry, with ADV in metal industry, with RD and NX in paper industry and with MKT in transport industry as the mean level of OTE is lesser than the critical level of

OTE beyond which its positive effect can be achieved. Further increase in OTE is recommended to derive its positive marginal effect on these strategic variables which will accentuate the further increase in OTE.

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